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NEW APPROACHES FOR SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT OF POORLY WATER SOLUBLE DRUG: - AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

A success of formulation depends on how efficiently it makes the drug available at the site of action. The solubility is the one of the most challenging aspects in formulation and development of dosage forms 40% of the new chemical entities currently being are poorly water soluble drug or lipophilic. Poorly water soluble drugs after oral administration often require high doses to reach therapeutic plasma concentration. Solubility is the phenomenon of dissolution of solid in liquid phase to give a homogenous system. There are various techniques which are used to improve or enhance the solubility of poorly soluble drugs, which include physical and chemical modification and other methods like salt formation, particle size reduction, solvent evaporation solid dispersion and so forth. Solid dispersion is the one of the techniques adopted for formulation of such drugs.

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INTRODUCTION

The therapeutic effectiveness of drug is depending upon solubility, bioavailability, and dissolution rate. There are many routes of drug administration but the oral drug delivery system is most preferred route due to patient compliance and ease of ingestion. In case of oral route there is several limited absorption of poorly water soluble drugs from g.i.t tract. Thus this system shows low bioavailability and poor pharmacological response 40% of newly developed chemical entities are lipophilic and fail to reach in the market formulation due to their low solubility behavior. So, it remains one of the most challenging aspects in the formulation development. To overcome these problems, various strategies till date have been applied to enhance solubility including pro-drug formation, β -CD Complexation use of surfactants, salt formation, etc. This review gives a view all about the development and different approaches enhancing the solubility and dissolution characteristics of hydrophobic drugs ^[1-4].

SOLUBILITY:

It is defined in quantitative terms as the concentration of solute in a saturated solution at certain temperature and pressure. Qualitatively it is defined as the spontaneous interaction between two or more substances to form homogenous or molecular dispersion. According to united state pharmacopeia (USP) solubility is defined as number of millilitres of solvent in which 1g of solute will be dissolved. In Indian pharmacopeia solubility is defined as ^[5-6]

Terms	Parts of solvent required to dissolved one part of solute
Very soluble	<1
Freely soluble	1-10
Soluble	10-30
Sparingly soluble	30-100
Slightly soluble	100-1000
Very slightly soluble	1000-10,000
Practically insoluble	>10000

BIOPHARMACEUTICS CLASSIFICATION SYSTEM:

The BCS is based on its aqueous solubility and intestinal permeability". 85% of the most sold drugs in the United States and Europe are orally administered. According to the BCS drug substances can be classified in four classes described as follow ^[7-8]

Class	Solubility	Permeability	Drugs	Characteristics Features
I	High	High	Propranolol, Diltiazem, Verapamil etc.	Well absorption orally.
II	Low	High	Itraconazole, Phenytoin, Nifedipine etc.	Variable absorption due to solubility limitation
III	High	Low	Ranitidine, Ciprofloxacin, Insulin etc.	Variable absorption due to permeability limitation.
IV	Low	Low	Methotrexate, Chlorothiazides, Furosemide etc.	Very small absorption due to solubility and permeability.

NEED FOR SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT:

More than 40% new chemical entities developed in pharmaceutical industry are practically insoluble in water. Solubility is one of the important parameter to achieve a desired concentration in systemic circulation for pharmacological response. A poorly water soluble drug shows less drug absorption which leads to variation in bioavailability and cause gastrointestinal mucosal toxicity. Therapeutic effectiveness of drug and pharmacological response mainly depends on solubility and bioavailability.

BIOAVAILABILITY:

Bioavailability (BA) is a term used in pharmacology and nutritional and environmental sciences. In pharmacology, it refers to the degree and rate at which an administered drug is absorbed by the body's circulatory system, the systemic circulation. It is one of the essential tools in pharmacokinetics since it determines the correct dosage for non-intravenous administration of a drug. Poor aqueous solubility is caused by mainly two factors ^[9-10]

- High lipophilicity.
- Strong intermolecular interaction.

VARIOUS TECHNIQUES FOR SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT ^[11-12]:

Physical modification	Chemical modification	Other methods
Particle size reduction	pH modification	Co-crystallization
Micro-ionization	Salts	Co-solvency
Nano-suspension	Soluble pro-drugs	Hydro-trophy
Modification of the crystal habit		Solvent deposition
Polymorphs		Porous-micro-particle technology
Pseudo polymorphs		Nanotechnology approaches
Complexation		
Use of complexing agents		
Solubilisation by surfactants		

SOLID DISPERSION:

Sekiguchi and obi' firstly proposed the concept of the Solid dispersion. According to this solid dispersion is the most commonly used technique for improving the dissolution and bioavailability of poorly soluble.

'Sekiguchi and obi' defined as solid dispersion is a group of solid products consisting of at least two different components, that is hydrophilic matrix and hydrophobic matrix. In this solid dispersion the matrix may be crystalline or amorphous. The drug can be dispersed molecularly, in amorphous particles or in crystalline particles.

Oral bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs is enhanced because these drugs show low and erratic levels of absorption. To overcome these problems water-soluble carrier are used.^[13-14]

EXAMPLES OF COMMERCIALY AVAILABLE SOLID DISPERSIONS

Brand name	Drug	Carrier	Manufacturer	Dosage form
Spornox	Janssen	Itraconazole	HPMC	Capsule
Intelence	Tibotec	Etravirin	HPMC	Tablet
Certican	Novartis	Everolimus	HPMC	Tablet
Kaletra	Abott	Lopinavir , ritonavir	PVPA	Tablet
Gris-PEG	Pedinol Pharmacal.inc.	Griseofulvin	PEG-6000	Tablet
Rezulin	Parke Davis	Troglitazone	HPMC	Tablet
Isoptin SR-E	Abbott	Verapamil	HPC/ HPMC	Tablet
Nivadil	Fujisawa	Nivaldipine	HPMC	Tablet

TYPES OF SOLID DISPERSION:

Solid dispersion consists of hydrophilic matrix and hydrophobic drug. So, matrix can be crystalline or amorphous in nature. A drug can be dispersed molecularly in any of particles.

These are classified on the basis of

- Carriers used
- Molecular arrangement^[15]

ON THE BASIS OF CARRIERS, CARRIERS ARE DIVIDED INTO THREE CLASSES

- First class
- Second class
- Third class

First class:

Solid dispersion was described by Sekiguchi and Obi in 1961. They noted that the formulation of eutectic mixtures improve the rate of drug release and thus increase bioavailability of poorly soluble drug. This solid dispersion was prepared by using various crystalline carriers such as Urea, Sugar. These two carriers were the first carriers to be employed in solid dispersion.

Disadvantage:

The main disadvantage of first class Solid dispersion is crystalline nature which leads to less solubility as compare to amorphous form; however, they possess good thermodynamic stability.

Second class: In this class instead of crystalline carriers' amorphous carrier were used to disperse drugs which are generally polymers. Polymeric carriers have been the most successful for the solid dispersions, because they are able to originate amorphous solid dispersion.

Figure1: Classification of Polymers.

Third class:

Recently it has been shown that the dissolution profile can be improved if the carrier has surface activity or self-emulsifying properties. Hence result in increased bioavailability: Examples: Polaxamer 407, Gelucire 44/14, Compritol 888 ATO27, and Inulin^[16-17].

Figure: 2, Classification of solid dispersion.

ON THE BASIS OF MOLECULAR ARRANGEMENT, THESE ARE CLASSIFIED AS

1. Eutectics
2. Amorphous precipitations in crystalline matrix
3. Solid solutions
 - a. Continuous solid solutions
 - b. Discontinuous solid solutions
 - c. Sub-stitutional solid solutions
 - d. Interstitial solid solutions.
4. Glass suspensions and solutions^[19-20]

Eutectics-

Eutectics mixtures are usually prepared by cooling a co-melt of the two compounds in order to obtain a physical mixture of very fine crystals of the two components^[21].

Figure: 3, Eutectic phase system diagram.

Solid solutions-

These solutions consist of one phase irrespective of other component. In this, drug first dissolved in a carrier which has relatively good aqueous solubility as a means of improving the bioavailability. The drug particle size is reduced^[22-24].

These are further classified as

- a) According to their miscibility
- b) According to way in which the solvate molecules are distributed in solvandum.

According to miscibility-

Continuous solid solution- In this, the components are miscible in all proportions. This means that the bonding strength between two components is stronger than bonding strength between molecules of each of the individual components^[25].

Figure: 3, continuous solid solution phase diagram.

Discontinuous solid solution- The solubility of the component in the other component is limited

Figure4: discontinuous solid solution phase diagram.

According to solvate molecules-

Substitutional solid solution- In this, substitution is only possible when the size of the solute molecules differ by less than 15% or so from that of solvent molecules.

Figure5: substitution solid solution phase diagram.

Interstitial solid solution- In interstitial solid solution, the dissolved molecules occupy the interstitial space between the solvent molecules. In this, molecular diameter of solute molecules should not be greater than 0.59 of the solvent molecule's diameter [26-27].

Figure 6: Interstitial solid solution phase diagram.

Amorphous precipitation in crystalline matrix-

In amorphous solid solution, the solute molecules are dispersed irregularly and molecularly within the amorphous solvent. Carriers such as urea and sugar (sucrose, galactose and dextrose) are used in earlier studies but now's day carriers such as cellulose derivatives, PVP, PEG etc have been utilized ^[28].

Figure7: Amorphous solid solution phase diagram.

Glass suspension and solutions-

Glass suspension is a mixture where the glassy solvents contains the suspended precipitated particles. Glass solutions are homogenous glassy system in which solute dissolve in glass carriers. It is characterized by transparency and brittleness below the glass transforming temperature. On heating it softens progressively and continuously without a sharp melting point ^[29].

PREPARATION METHODS OF SOLID DISPERSION ^[30-31]

SOLVENT EVAPORATION METHOD:

In this, solid dispersion is prepared by dissolving the Drug and carrier in an organic solvent. After complete dissolution, the solvent is evaporated under control pressure. Then, solid mass is ground, sieved and dried ^[32].

Advantages:

These drugs and carriers cannot be thermally decomposed because a very low temperature is used for evaporation of organic solvents.

KNEADING METHOD:

A mixture of accurately weighed drug and carrier is mixed and prepared in mortar and then moisten in methanol. Now, the moisten mass is kneaded for 30 min and for 24 hrs. The paste is dried and sieved to produce fine powder and stored in desiccator for further use ^[33].

MELT METHOD:

In this method, drug and carrier is weighed and mixed in glass mortar and pestle. The mixture is melted at particular temperature to get the homogenous dispersion. It is then cooled to obtain the dispersion and then pulverized and sieved ^[34].

LYOPHILIZATION METHOD: also called freeze drying.

- Lyophilization is dehydration or drying process.
- Lyophilization has been thought of molecular mixing technique where drug and carrier are co- dissolved in a common solvent, frozen and sublimed to obtain lyophilized molecular dispersion.
- This technique was proposed as an alternative method to solvent evaporation
- Its applicable for thermo labile or otherwise unstable in aqueous solution for prolonged storage periods, but that are stable in dry

Principal:

Based on the phenomena sublimation. Sublimation can take place at pressure and below triple point (i.e.4.579mmHg and 0.0099⁰ c). Freeze drying of pharmaceutical is carried out at temperature of -10⁰ to - 40⁰ c.

Advantages:

- Liquid are processed with ease in aseptic processing
- Stability studies of drug is increase
- Drug gets easily dissolved when reconstituted^[36]

CO-PRECIIPITATION:

This technique is widely used for improving the dissolution characteristics of poorly water soluble drugs. In this method, drug and carrier are mixed in an organic solvent. On precipitation, drug and carrier are separated and separation is mainly depends upon solubility properties of drug and the carrier.

In this method, required quantity of drug and carrier were added in a solvent to obtain a clear solution. The solution was dried at room temperature and then placed in incubator for 12 hours At last; it was passed through sieve ^[37].

SPRAY DRYING:

In this method, the drug and polymer are dissolved in methanol to obtain a clear solution. To remove the solvent or methanol mixture is then spray dried using a scale dryer. Due to this method, the drug which obtained in amorphous form can also be obtained in crystalline form^[38].

MELT EXTRUSION:

Accurately weighed drug and carrier are prepared by hot stage extrusion using a co- rotating twin screw extruder. The mixtures are mixed at melting temperature and the product obtained is cooled and milled^[39].

MELT AGGLOMERATION:

In this method, the solid dispersion is prepared in conventional high shear mixers by heating the mixture of drug, carrier and excipients to a temperature within the carrier^[40].

USE OF SURFACTANTS:

To increase the solubility, various surfactants is used. It works by reducing surface tension and interfacial tension which ultimately reduce the hydrophobicity of drug. Gelucires is a new class of surfactant which is used in solid dispersion and identified by HLB values^[41].

GEL ENTRAPMENT:

Carrier is dissolved in organic solvent to form a clear and transparent gel. Then, drug is taken and dissolved in gel by sonication. Organic solvent is evaporated and prepared solid dispersion is pulverized and finally sieved.

DRUG CARRIER MISCIBILITY**Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC):**

DSC used to determine the amount of crystalline material of solid dispersion. In this characterization, samples are heated at a specific temperature and constant temperature. Thermal events can be a glass to rubber transition, (re)crystallization, melting or degradation. Furthermore, the melting and (re)cry-stylization energy can be quantified. The melting energy can be used to detect the amount of crystalline material.

Powder X-ray Diffraction (PXRD):

This characterization is used to qualitatively detect material with long range order. And sharper diffraction peaks which indicate crystalline material. Now a days X-Ray equipment is semi quantitative.

DRUG CARRIER INTERACTION:**Infrared spectroscopy (IR) and Fourier Transformed Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR):**

This technique is used to detect the variation in the energy distribution of interactions between drug and polymer. Sharp vibrational bands during the IR study indicate crystallinity. Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to accurately detect crystallinity and functional group ranging from 1 to 99% in pure material^[44].

PHYSICAL STRUCTURE:**Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM):**

The principal of SEM is based on an electron beam is focused onto the sample surface kept in a vacuum by electromagnetic lenses. Then beam scanned over the surface and then fed to the detector and cathode ray tube through an amplifier, where the images are formed. SEM is mainly used to study the surface of polymers, metals. It is also used for both topography and Compositional analysis

SOUBILITY STUDIES:

Solubility studies are used to find out the solubility behavior of solid dispersion. There are different types of solvent system and body fluids are used to find out the solubility behavior. Solubility studies can be determined by either saturation solubility or phase solubility studies^[46].

DISSOLUTION STUDIES:

In-vitro dissolution studies are used to find out dissolution behavior of the drug and also demonstrate the bioavailability or bio-equivalence of the drug product through in-vitro / in-vivo correlation (IVIVC)

CONCLUSION

One of the most challenging problems in pharmaceutical field is to increase the bioavailability of orally administered poorly water soluble drug More than 40% NCEs (new chemical entities) developed in pharmaceutical industry are practically insoluble in water. Solubility is one of the important parameter to achieve a desired concentration in systemic circulation for pharmacological response. Hence, enhancing of solubility and bioavailability is the major challenge faced by formulation scientist. So for enhancing the solubility many techniques have been used, solid dispersion being one of them. Solid dispersion has been used since past decade for the enhancement of solubility. However, the commercial development of this technique requires overcoming the problems such as scale up, cost effectiveness and instability of drugs.

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